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A New Platform for Case-Based and Visual Learning in Perioperative Medicine

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Editorial

Welcome to the First Issue of Anesthesia and Critical Care Reports and Imaging (J Anesth Crit Care Rep Imaging)

It is a real pleasure to share with you the very first issue of Anesthesia and Critical Care Reports and Imaging (ANCRI). This new journal has been created as a space to share experiences, ideas, and images that can help us improve care in anesthesia, perioperative medicine, and critical care.

In medicine, we learn not only from large studies but also from real cases. Case reports, images, and videos give us a chance to see unusual situations, unexpected complications, or creative ways of solving problems. In anesthesia and critical care—where decisions must often be made quickly—these kinds of practical lessons are especially valuable. Sometimes, one image or short clip can teach more than pages of text [1,2].

ANCRI brings together two areas that are usually separate:

Case reports and series (2–15 cases): showing rare situations, unusual patient responses, or lessons learned from daily practice.

Clinical imaging and POCUS: sharing high-quality images, ultrasound findings, and perioperative imaging that support safe and evidence-based care.

By combining case-based learning with visual medicine, our goal is to make ANCRI a trusted source of practical knowledge that complements traditional research articles.

The journal is open access, peer-reviewed, and double-blind. It will be published four times a year (March, June, September, December). Our aim is to maintain high editorial standards while keeping the content freely available for the global medical community.

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We believe that the heart of this journal will be its contributors and readers. We warmly invite anesthesiologists, intensivists, pain specialists, and perioperative physicians from all over the world to share their cases, images, and ideas. Together, we can create a resource that reflects both the diversity of our daily work and our common goal—better patient care. On behalf of the editorial team, we would like to sincerely thank the authors who contributed to this first issue, our reviewers, and all colleagues who supported the start of this journey. We look forward to growing with you and shaping ANCRI into a valuable platform for learning and sharing.

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